

Impact of non-oil Revenue collection/mobilization on Public Financial Management in South Sudan: a case study on National Ministry of Finance and Planning

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Abstract:

The study aims to look at the effect of non-oil revenue collection/mobilization on public financial management, as well as the obstacles that non-oil revenue collection faces in South Sudan. Non-oil revenue faces several challenges, ranging from effective service delivery to non-oil revenue collection. The key goal is to determine the main source of non-oil revenue collection, develop public financial control and management, examine mechanisms for dealing with non-oil revenue collection issues, and ensure effective and consistent management of non-oil resources under South Sudan government policies and objectives. The report aims to eliminate or minimize to a bare minimum the issues associated with non-oil revenue generation, non-oil revenue administration, tax base penetration, and difficulties in recognizing non-oil revenue mobilization. Other goals include proposing and designing a database solution for efficient property ownership and tax collection control, as well as proposing a network solution for linking local governments and land sector agencies. The research was based primarily on secondary data gathered from non-oil sales analyses and publications. Both descriptive and frequency analyses were used to interpret the data. Microsoft Excel was used as a data collection and presentation platform. Tables and graphs were used to display the information. The researchers looked at the difficulties that come with collecting non-oil revenue in this report. Due to the outbreak of pandemic covid-19, political unrest, and inaccessibility of certain non-oil revenue sources in South Sudan, it was discovered that the non-oil revenue pattern has not been stable. It was discovered that the organization does not keep a complete or accurate record of all taxable events or levies in its jurisdiction. There is no mechanism in place for keeping track of invoices and payments. Data on utilities, equipment, levies, and other items were done by hand, making it vulnerable to bribery, violence, and major non-oil revenue loss. The researchers suggest ways to improve non-oil revenue leakage along with property rate administration through the non-oil revenue task force. They introduce a non-oil revenue database method for capturing non-oil revenue, as well as a computerized non-oil revenue system to improve revenue capture and mitigate leakages. According to the report, policymakers should enact policies that support non-oil revenue management to maintain improved government financial efficiency in South Sudan.

Keywords: *Non-oil revenue, collection, Mobilization, public financial management, employees, accountability.*

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Introduction

The effect of non-oil revenue collection/mobilization on public financial management is investigated in this report. Non-oil revenue generation, public financial management, transparency, and economic activity regulation are all responsibilities of the Ministry of Finance and Planning, which also determines South Sudan's monetary policy and works to promote good, equitable, and sustainable economic development. It "manages the Government of the Republic of South Sudan's total non-oil revenue, spending, and funding, and provides the Government with guidance on South Sudan's general financial affairs in favor of the Government's economic and social objectives." Some of its responsibilities include "preparing the Central Government budget; developing tax policy and legislation; managing government borrowings on financial markets; determining expenditure allocations to various government institutions; transferring central grants to local governments, and developing regulatory policy for the country's financial sector in collaboration with the Ministry of Finance a." South Sudan's non-oil revenue, also known as national revenue, is money collected by a country from taxation and non-tax sources to fund government spending. The federal budget includes both taxes and expenditures, and both are critical instruments of the government's economic strategy. Non-oil sales can be increased by deflating the value of the government's currency in exchange for surplus revenue, allowing governments to lift the price of commodities unnecessarily. The Council of Ministers established the non-oil revenue task force in 2014 intending to enhance non-oil revenue collection/mobilization, as well as public financial management and transparency in South Sudan. -increasing spending priorities, fostering faster economic growth, and adhering to fiscal rules that restrict the government's non-oil revenue deficit to no more than 4% of GDP in 2016. Structured tax measures can generate substantial non-oil revenue. In the short and medium-term, a broad-based and comprehensive tax reform program is needed to address these goals and generate long-term revenue growth by broadening the basis of income and consumption taxes, closing loopholes and leakage created by corporate tax holidays, and widespread use of other associated tax expenditures, and creating incentives for the subnational tiers of government. Because of the need to take urgent measures to minimize dependence on oil, raise non-oil revenues, and reduce oil revenues to improve spending regulation, the effect of the positions of non-oil revenue collection/mobilization and public financial management in South Sudan was planned. Indeed, oil exports, which are crucial to the country's economy, have plummeted since July 2012, resulting in a budget deficit of 1.2% of GDP in 2018, 11.3 percent in 2019, and 4.9 percent in 2020. (2020). Furthermore, the current project is a project institutional support, financed by both grant and loan funding, that will supplement other donor investments aimed at addressing capacity needs in two interrelated areas: capacity building at the country level and non-oil revenues at both the national and state levels, as well as enhancing financial management, openness, and accountability.

Our objectives are (i) to identify the main source of non-oil revenue collection in South Sudan, (ii) to establish the public financial control and management, (iii) to investigate mechanism of managing the challenges in non-oil revenue collection & (iv) to ensure sustainable management of non-oil resources, efficient and transparent manner, in line with the South Sudan government policies and objectives and we investigated four research questions (i) What are the main sources of non-oil revenue collection in South Sudan? (ii) What are the roles of non-oil-Revenue in public financial control and accountability? (iii)What are the mechanisms of managing the challenges in non-oil revenue collection? (iv) Does management of non-oil resources, affect the allocated public finance for efficient and transparent manner, with the government policies and objectives?

The research would aid in the growth of South Sudan's infrastructure. For eg, African resource construction ARC, Rhino Stars Company Limited, is building roads and bridges. Academic scholars in the area of public financial accounting, such as university students, will learn from the study. South Sudanese policymakers, including the National Ministry of Finance and Planning, the Ministry of Commerce and Trade, the National Revenue Authority NRA, and the Ministry of Petroleum, received assistance on non-oil revenue generation and control.

Figure 1: Conceptual Frame work of non-oil revenue

REVIEW OF THE LITERATURES

South Sudan Public Financial Management and Accountability Act, 2011

The National Legislative Assembly, with the President of the Republic of South Sudan's assent, enacts the National Revenue Fund and Reserve Funds in accordance with the terms of Article 55 (3) (b) read along with Article 85 (1) of the Transitional Constitution of the Republic of South Sudan, 2011. Both taxes raised for or by the government will be pooled and managed by the Ministry of Finance and Planning. Both accounts and sub-funds into which monies owed to the government are collected, invested, and published shall be referred to as the National Revenue Fund. Specific tax accounts for each revenue component, including oil revenue, non-oil revenue, grants, transfers, loan proceeds, monies collected for the purposes of Financing Projects, Sub-Funds, and special funds and accounts referred to in the Constitution, shall be maintained by the Ministry of Finance and Planning, and they shall collectively form the National Revenue Fund. All monies accruing to the government, including those already paid into the National Revenue Fund, that are not allocated for spending by the Assembly by the Appropriation Act or a Supplementary Appropriation Law become part of the government's legal account, also known as Reserve Funds. Any surplus funds raised and invested in the National Revenue Fund during the Financial Year more than the annual budget revenue projections will be added to the Reserve Funds as appropriated Reserve Funds that will remain unspent at the end of the Financial Year. Non-Oil revenue forms not covered by non-oil revenue resources are grouped as non-oil revenue in South

Sudan. They essentially consist of three non-oil revenue sources: corporate income tax, customs, and excise duty, and value-added taxes. Non-oil revenue covers, among other things, levies, public debt, loans, Personal Income Tax (PIT), Customs and Excise Duties (CED), Companies Income Tax (CIT), Value Added Tax, Education Tax, support, and landing fees from Juba International and Wau AirPort. South Sudan's tax system is a major determinant of macroeconomic indexes for both developed and developing economies; therefore, there is a connection between tax structure and economic growth in either country, according to the World Bank (Libabatu, 2014).

Tax: According to Omotoso (2001), tax is a mandatory levy imposed by the government on the profits and estates of individuals and businesses as specified by the South Sudanese government's Decrees and Laws, regardless of the specific service rendered by the payer in return. Tax is the proportion or sum of money that may be paid to the government as tax from an individual's or organization's earnings and gains. Individuals and institutions must fulfill this duty as long as they are in operation. According to Akintoye and Tashie (2013), the ability of individuals or citizens to pay taxes is very critical and cannot be overlooked. They recommended that the government pay heed to the variables that affect residents' ability to pay taxes and work to strengthen them.

Tax Revenue: The income obtained by a jurisdiction's government from oil and non-oil operations is known as tax revenue. Revenues from tax structures are referred to as tax revenues. Oil revenue and non-oil revenue are the two types of revenue that a country like South Sudan generates. South Sudan's government income is divided into two key sources: oil and non-oil sales, according to Ihendinihu et al. (2014).

Measurement of Tax Revenue

Business Income Tax (CIT), Personal Income Tax (PIT), Value Added Tax (VAT), and Customs and Excise Duties are the mechanisms deemed sufficient to calculate non-oil tax revenue throughout this report (CED).

Business Income Tax (BIT)

According to Okeke, Mbonu and Ndubuisi (2018), a company is defined as any company or entity established by or under any law in force in South Sudan or elsewhere. The institution responsible for the registration of companies in South Sudan is the Ministry of Justice and constitutional affairs. According to Ogbonna and Appah (2016) defines Companies Income Tax (CIT) as a tax levied on the profit of companies (excluding profit from companies engaged in upstream operations) accruing in, derived from, brought into or received in South Sudan in respect of any business, rent, premium, dividends, interest, royalties and any other source of annual profit. Hence, Ariwodola (2000) resolved that the companies' income tax is chargeable on the global profits of South Sudanese companies irrespective of whether or not they are brought into or received in South Sudan. The share of the profits of foreign firms derived from such firm's operations in South Sudan. (Dividends, interests or royalties due to foreign companies) is assessed at ten percent (10%) withholding tax rate. Companies Income Tax (CIT) is charged at 30 percent rate of assessable profits of companies.

Personal Income Tax (PIT): Personal income refers to income of individuals, families or communities arising from employment, business, trade, profession, or vocation (Dandago & Alabede, 2001). Personal Income Tax (PIT) (Amendment) Act 2011 defines personal income tax as the tax imposed by the government on the incomes of individuals and corporation soles. This tax is levied on individuals, body of individuals or corporation soles based on their level of income or profits. The relevant tax authority responsible for the collection of Personal Income Tax (PIT) is the State Internal Revenue Service's of the respective states and the non-oil Revenue Services respectively. While the State Internal Revenue Service is responsible for

the collection of taxes of individuals, body of individuals or corporation soles who are deemed to be resident that year in their respective states, the Federal Inland Revenue Service collects personal income taxes of individuals, body of individuals or corporation soles resident in the Federal Capital Territory (FCT), members of the military and police, South Sudan. On foreign mission, and non-resident individuals this tax is easy to collect as it is deducted at source by the appropriate tax authority (Cislac & Abu, 2012). However, despite its ease of non-oil revenue collection, it has remained the most disappointing, non-performing, unsatisfactory and problematic in the history of South Sudanese tax system

Customs and Excise Duties: Customs tax, sometimes referred to as import duty, was first introduced in 2005. Customs duties are the oldest form of modern tax revenue in South Sudan, and they are the key revenue stream for the government, since they are paid by importers of specific goods. Customs duties are taxes imposed on products and services imported into South Sudan. They are calculated as a proportion of the value of the goods or services imported, or as a set sum based on the quantity of goods imported (Buba, 2007). To widen South Sudan's oil revenue base, excise duties were imposed on a number of commodities in 2011. Excise duty is a levy imposed on locally made products, their sale, and their use (such as alcohol, tobacco, petrol, manufacture, and so on). Excise duties are charges levied by the government at various rates on particular goods manufactured in a region. These fees are levied on domestic products manufactured in the United States, as opposed to imported commodities, and are mostly imposed to generate revenue. The main distinction between the two taxes is that, although excise duty is imposed by the government on commodities and items produced domestically, customs duty is imposed on goods imported from other countries. The cumulative amount of import duties received by the customs and excise department is known as duty duties. Depending on the tax base, excise taxes are either "selective or general" or "specific or ad valorem." Customs and excise duties are an important component of non-oil revenue, and they have remained a key revenue stream in South Sudan both before and after the discovery of oil, contributing significantly to national growth over time. According to Buba (2007), the Central Government imposes customs and excise taxes, fines, tariffs, and other levies on imports, exports, and regulatory rates, and the South Sudanese Custom Services is tasked with collecting them.

Value Added Tax (VAT): VAT (Value Added Tax) is a tax charged on the value that a retailer or manufacturer of products or services adds to them before selling them. The need to increase government revenue from non-oil sources following volatility in oil revenue due to the foreign price surplus necessitated the implementation of VAT. The South Sudan Revenue Services administers VAT, which was implemented into the South Sudanese tax system in fiscal year with the promulgation of VAT to replace the Sales Tax Act at a rate of 5%. Value added tax (VAT) is a multi-step tax levied on the extra value of products manufactured or services provided as they go through various phases of manufacturing, delivery, and service rendering. It is largely borne by the final customer, although it is raised at each stage of the production and service chain (Bird, 2005). According to Umeora (2013), value added tax is a tax on the estimated retail value added to a product or service at each stage of production or delivery, with the additions ultimately being added on products and services that carry the tax cost or occurrence when the tax charged on purchase of goods and services cannot be recovered. The disparity between a firm's revenue (output) and transactions (input) from other businesses is its value added. A firm's value added is the amount of value it adds to the products or services it produces by using such manufacturing factors such as space, labour, money, and entrepreneurial capacity. A section of VAT Decree No. specifically exempted some goods and services from tax. There are products and services that are solely concerned with people's well-being and are important to human growth and progress. Health products and services, medicinal equipment, essential food commodities, books and instructional materials,

plants and equipment for use in export production zones (EPZs) or free trade zones (FTZs), and fees on stock exchange transactions are among the goods and services excluded from vat (PWC, 2018). VAT is a sales tax that is comparatively easy to enforce and impossible to circumvent, according to the South Sudan Revenue Service, and it has been widely adopted around the world.

Traditional sources of non-oil revenue in South Sudan

Councils may collect money from a variety of ways to finance their activities. The funding streams can be classified as council-owned, government/donor-funded, loans/borrowing, and so on. It is important for tax collectors to understand the different types of revenue. State taxes/rates, levies, fines and costs, for example, are examples of common sources.

Levies: Levies are taxes on economic activities taking place within council jurisdiction; levies are imposed may, make by-laws imposing all or any of the following levies:

- a) Livestock levy imposed on animals exported out of the district.
- b) Business Licenses on those conducting business in the district.
- c) Fish Levy paid by traders exporting fish out of the district.

Fees or Charges: Fees and charges are imposed for the services rendered by the council, to the residents living within their boundaries. Councils derive power to effect fees and charges, South Sudan, impose fees or charges payable to the Council:

- a) For any license or permit issued under any by-law or regulation made under this Act;
- b) For any service or facility provided or goods or documents supplied by the non-oil revenue taskforce in pursuance of or in connection with the discharge

Local taxes: A tax levied and collected by a city, municipality or a district council. Local taxes are collected in order to fund local government services, for example, maintenance of local roads. Examples of local taxes are; Property Tax (rates) and Personal Levy.

It is imperative to note that taxes finances services cannot be linked to a specific consumer, unlike fees and charges.

License: A license is granted as permission to do something or use something. Licenses are legal documents (certificates) issued by the local authorities to citizens within their jurisdiction to carry on a trade (especially in alcoholic beverages). Most of the licenses have been turned into direct levy except liquor, dog license and firearm.

Permits: A permit is another type of license. Permits regulate safety and are typically granted following an inspection. Permits are granting authorization or a legal document giving permission to do business, e.g. for building occupancy, for health and fire, and for other types of activities, like operating a business which serves liquor.

ALTERNATIVE REVENUE SOURCES IN SOUTH SUDAN

Alternative funding options open to councils are discussed in this session. While these solutions may not be possible for all Councils, they provide officers with a useful frame of comparison to see what is viable in other areas of the country. Nontraditional sources of income, such as national assistance (grants), loans, land construction funds, donor aid, and so on, are examples of non-oil revenue sources. Non-oil revenue collectors may obtain non-oil revenue from a variety of non-traditional sources.

Sources of non-oil Revenue – How to Enhance Collection in South Sudan

The Ministry of Finance and Planning in South Sudan, as well as the National Revenue Authority, must be dedicated to maximizing revenue streams that are lawfully and administratively accessible. Councils must implement a broad set of changes to their practices, processes, personnel, and operational structure. The aim is to maximize the usage of each revenue stream in line with the Ministry of Finance's objectives and priorities. As a result, it's critical that revenue staff consider the different non-oil revenue streams and how

to improve their own revenue sources. Revenue Officers must assess the situation and evaluate their competitive edge, or the unique situation (s) that exist in their region.

Some of tools and Equipment Used in Non-oil Revenue Collection

Receipt books for nonoil revenue collection example, financial form 15 (FF15)

Collection summary sheets example, financial form 67 (FF67)

Copies of the revenue collection targets

Copies of financial act (Public Financial Management and Accountability Act, 2011)

Inventory of non-oil revenue forms

Chart of Account Manual

Bank deposit slips.

Identity cards

Date stamp pad and ink.

Calculator

Uniform

What Are Available Potential Non-oil Revenue Sources in South Sudan?

Public – Private Partnership

Public – Private Partnerships are another potential source of revenue for government, especially for the revenue required funding capital projects example cooperative Bank of South Sudan. There common public – private partnership models are discussed below:

Build – Operate – Transfer. A private sector firm acquires a franchise to finance, design, build and operate a facility for a specified period, during which time the government collects charges and pays the private operator. At the end of the period the facility reverts to the public sector.

Concession: A private firm is granted the right to provide and charge for a service. The vendor acquires the existing or builds a new one. The arrangement runs for a long period, after which the facility may be returned to the government

Operating and Management Contracts: The government retains the ownership of the facility, but contracts with a private firm to operate and maintain the facility. These three arrangements are not true privatization, where the actual facility is sold to a private vendor. In these arrangements, the Council retains an interest in the service and ultimately retains ownership of the facility

The ways of improving non-oil-revenue collection in South Sudan

Some Revenue agent inability to provide services or to carry out their mandated services has been attributed, among others, to in efficiency in revenue collection. In order to improve collection efficiency, councils should take into account the following:

- (i) Collecting and receipting every South Sudan pounds (SSP) due to the government
- (ii) Maintaining an up to date non-oil revenue database.
- (iii) Creating awareness to the community in advance, on new taxes, levies/fees /charges rates before the actual implementation.
- (iv) Setting collection targets, carrying out monitoring and reviews on a continuous basis.
- (v) Close supervision – frequently checking on revenue collectors at various collecting points.
- (vi) Improving infrastructure at non-oil revenue collecting points, e.g. barriers, sign posts, security lights etc.
- (vii) Being innovative by exploring other sources of non-oil revenue
- (viii) Sensitizing community on the importance of paying taxes to the government of South Sudan
- (ix) Rotation of non-oil revenue collectors
- (x) Sending bills and reminders on time

- (xi) Involving all departments in non-oil revenue collection such as the domestic tax, and South Sudan custom Service
- (xii) Training and incentive of non-oil revenue collectors should be given on time when they are deployed for smooth revenue collection and report standard in financial institutions of government of South Sudan
- (xiii) Forming a non-oil revenue collection monitoring team or task force under the supervision of the Ministry of Finance and Planning in order to ensure public finance accountability
- (xiv) Installation of computerized non-oil revenue collection software /equipments or machine

Attributes of a good non-oil Revenue Collector

Inadequacy in non-oil revenue collection is to some extent, as result of bad or negative attitude of those entrusted to collect non-oil revenue. Therefore, it is important that revenue collectors are adequately trained in order to enhance non-oil revenue collection. Below are some of the attributes of a good revenue collector:

- (i) Able to speak with confidence.
- (ii) Have a work plan that will guide in fulfilling revenue collection targets.
- (iii) Having adequate knowledge about the various sources of non-oil revenue.
- (iv) Presentable
- (v) Sober minded.
- (vi) Hard working – committed to work.
- (vii) Good communication skills.
- (viii) Be accountable.

Faithfulness – after collections all the monies should be handed over to main cashier.

Available on duty all the time.

Teachable on non-oil revenue collection procedures

Challenges Faced By the Revenue Collectors in South Sudan: the key challenges are

- (i) Inadequate security in some area where non-oil revenue are generate
- (ii) Lack of identification of oil revenue collectors deployed at the revenues stations across the country
- (iii) Lack of transport for non-oil revenue collector staff Bus for the mobility
- (iv) Resistance to payment of fees, levies / charges by some customers.
- (v) Inadequate service provision hence hindering payment of fees / levies / charges.
- (vi) Lack of orientation of new non-oil revenue collectors by the revenue expert
- (vii) Inadequate knowledge on legal documents relating to non-oil revenue collection
- (viii) Differences in Levies and Charges between in non-oil revenues institutions
- (ix) Poor road network
- (x) Lack of knowledge by tax payers why they pay taxes to the government
- (xi) Training Manual on non-oil Revenue Collection method and policies should be develop
- (xii) Political Interference in non-oil revenue Collection

Solutions to the Challenges faced by the Non-oil Revenue Collectors in South Sudan

- (i) Providing government Policies to the non-oil Revenue Collectors
- (ii) Providing Identity cards and Uniforms to the non-oil Revenue Collectors
- (iii) Allocating a vehicle specifically for non-oil revenue collection
- (iv) Sensitize the community on the need to pay Council fees, levies / charges
- (v) Provision of service to the community in South Sudan
- (vi) Involvement of the none oil revenue collectors in the planning and budgeting

- (vii) Providing basic training and orientation to the non-oil revenue collectors
- (viii) Providing relevant legal documents timely to the non-oil revenue collectors
- (ix) Harmonize levies and charges in bordering Countries

Roles of Stakeholders in Non-oil Revenue Mobilization and Collection Process in South Sudan

Citizens: Citizens are non-oil revenue payers: they pay the requisite taxes, fines, permits, and costs, and so demand improved programs and outcomes. To ensure ownership, tax policies must be developed in coordination with citizens, and the government must meet with citizens on a regular basis and respond quickly to concerns posed by citizens. For encouraging voluntary compliance in paying dues, a good partnership between residents and the Council is important. Citizens can be effective watchdogs against misappropriation of public funds, and they should be encouraged to offer this service to the government in South Sudan at all levels.

Revenue task force: Make policies and decisions/resolutions on local governance and development for a local area. The policies or decisions concerning non-oil revenue mobilization campaigns if favorable can improve non-oil revenue collection in the South Sudan

Ensure that there is transparency and accountability in the operation of the South Sudan

Conduct civic education on Council's duties to the citizens of a local government area and to take part in campaigns for revenue collection.

Finance Committee: This Monitors activities and policies that regulate, control and manage public finances of the public financial institution, that is, monitors non-oil revenue collection and usage, monitors expenditure of the government, advises on and monitors application of rates and levies, checks irregularities regarding financial transactions. Supports development and implementation of budgets

Director of Accounts/Revenue in Treasurer: Coordinates and manages development and implementation of the budget. Raises money and ensure efficient use to advance best interest of the renders regular and fair account of stewardship and performance of the Council's money.

Ensure that controls which guide the revenue staff (and monitor its financial performance by ensuring that accounting rules and procedures) are in place. Provide financial advice to the members of the revenue and reconciliation, the officers and the general public through the revenues collectors and makes periodic statements in terms of expenditure.

Non-oil revenue collectors: Using a general receipt book, raise non-oil taxes in different ways from tax payers and other subordinate revenue collectors such as market masters' bus station officers. Account for all revenue received by using an accurate cashbook or logging all revenue collected, and send all non-oil revenue collected to head office on a regular basis. Receive all requisite receipt and business fee books from head office for use of his / her field of duties. Keep track of how the general receipt books and business fees books have been used. Subordinate collectors should be given market fees books and all other required books, and they should be held accountable to him. He or she will be in charge of supervising non-oil sales workers and setting revenue goals for his or her team. Produce annual non-oil revenue analyses and reports for high-level officials in the Ministry of Finance and Planning, as well as collaborate with other stakeholders, including the Ministry of Commerce, the Ministry of Petroleum, the Economic Committee, and other financial institutions, on all issues concerning non-oil revenue collection in South Sudan.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The use of a cross-sectional survey methodology was justified due to its cost-effectiveness, speed of data collection, and ability to understand a population from a small sample. Interviews were conceived, created, and conducted by the researchers, who also reviewed secondary data from the non-oil revenue and reconciliation unit's management. Ministry of Finance and Planning, Directorate of Accounts Members of the executive team, heads of departments, treasury, and finance-related offices were all targeted. The decision (purposive)

sampling methodology was used for this analysis. Purposive sampling is where researchers choose who to include in the survey on purpose. Non-oil tax records and reports, chart of accounts, national budget books, and public finance act books were used to collect secondary data. The collected data was interpreted to add context to the study's basic goal. Statistical instruments such as percentages, charts, and graphs were used to tabulate and display the results. The qualitative findings of the survey were explained using narrative interpretation.

Major Revenue-generating Agencies in public sector			
1.	Ministry of Justice	2.	Ministry of Environment
3.	Electricity Corporation	4.	Ministry of Land and Housing
5.	Ministry of Investment	6.	Ministry of Agriculture
7.	Ministry of Petroleum	8.	Ministry of Animal Resources & fisheries
9.	Ministry of Mining	10.	Ministry of Water Resources and Irrigation
11.	Ministry of Health	12.	Urban water corporation
13.	Ministry of Trade	14.	Relief and rehabilitation commission
15.	Ministry of Information	16.	Judiciary of South Sudan
17.	SSBC/ Gateway	18.	Ministry of Labor
19.	Ministry of Foreign Affairs	20.	Immigration and Passport
21.	Ministry of General Education	22.	Tourism and Hotels & management (Ministry of wild life)
23.	Ministry of Higher Education	24.	South Sudan Civil Aviation Juba
25.	Ministry of Transport	26.	Media Authority
27.	Ministry of Road	28.	Central Bank of South Sudan (licenses)

Source: Ministry Finance and Planning

DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Data Presentation Sources of non-oil Revenue in public sector in South Sudan

Others shared non-oil revenue

Transfers from the state are the other major non-oil income source for municipalities. This can be divided into two types of flows: the first is direct assistance for localities' wages and pensions, and the second is the allocation of the localities' share of the Sudan's tax revenue. The Local Development Act of 2003 (Article 27, Chapter 7) specifies which of the state's revenues should be shared with the municipalities.

Individual corporation taxes, VAT, and capital gains taxes are among them.

Localities share of the state's taxes, fees and duties Non-oil Revenue sources Percentage to the locality in South Sudan/Sudan

S/No	Revenue sources	Percentage to the locality
1.	Fees on vehicle licenses and driving licenses	60%
2.	Real estate tax	60%
3.	State's stamp duty	40%
4.	Personal income (State) tax	40%
5.	Land and river transportation fees	40%
6.	Fees on the registration of clubs, societies, and associations	40%
7.	Sale proceeds of investment lands	40%
8.	Agricultural and animal production tax	60%
9.	Service fees	60%
10.	Fees on veterinary examination and fees on slaughtering and slaughterhouses	60%
11.	Fees on residential plans, designation and allocation of lands for residential, commercial, agricultural, industrial, and investment purposes	40%
12.	12. Fees on the State's forestry products	60%
13.	13. Value added taxes	60%

Source: Sudan Local government laws from various Sates (2003)

Non-oil Revenues shared between state government units and local government units are to be divided on each month based on actual flow of Non-oil revenues as set forth in the Local

Government Law of 2006 as amended in 2010. The Local Government Laws of the States also refer to the following 'other revenue sources' for the localities: The state subsidies, Grants, loans and credit facilities approved by the Government., Return on investments placed by the localities, Self-help and popular participation, Percentage of the oil and mining revenues as a percentage allocated for the state ,Percentage of the proceeds of governmental projects and national reserves, Percentage of the Non-oil revenues/proceeds of tourism, Percentage of foreign grants and aid, Percentage of the taxes and fees on cross-border trade in accordance with the national legislations, Percentage of any other taxes assigned under the Law for the state, of these sources, "self-help and popular participation" contribute substantially to own revenues in some localities

Major non-oil Revenue-Collecting Agencies (Institution), NRA Charges and Bank Changes

S/No	Banking Agencies	Agencies(Institutions)	NRA Charges	Bank Changes
1.	Nile commercial Bank	5%	2%	1%
2.	Cooperative Bank	5%	2%	1%
3.	Eco Bank South Sudan Branch	5%	2%	1%
4.	Ivory Bank South Sudan Branch	5%	2%	1%
5.	Kenya commercial Bank South Sudan Branch	5%	2%	1%
6.	Equity commercial Bank South Sudan Branch	5%	2%	1%
7.	Stanbic Bank South Sudan Branch	5%	2%	1%
8.	Buffalo commercial bank South Sudan Branch	5%	2%	1%

Source data: (Microsoft excel) Non-oil revenue/ Ministry of Finance and Planning

Non-oil revenue collected In South Sudanese Pound (SSP) 2016-2017

Month/years	Amount In SSP
Jul-16	980,616,346.89
Aug-16	490,683,782.01
Sep-16	1,332,518,598.52
Oct-16	1,241,213,366.18
Nov-16	2,102,352,888.97
Dec-16	1,407,893,163.24
Jan-17	913,963,678.55
Feb-17	1,556,392,470.94
Mar-17	1,614,199,473.05
Apr-17	5,966,926,100.67
Total Remittent	17,606,759,869.01

Source data: (Microsoft excel) Non-oil revenue/ Ministry of Finance and Planning

Non-Oil Revenue report South Sudan Civil Aviation report as From: Jan-Dec 2017

Months	Landing	Navigation	Security	Passages	Parking	Others	Total SSP
January	1,625,003	412,654	1,999,943	717,726	-	749,257	5,504,583
February	852,179	217,159	902,725	730,353	-	793,848	3,496,264
March	1,395,686	305,178	1,119,950	397,902	-	2,130,718	5,349,434
April	985,647	252,486	1,135,159	400,818	-	2,635,845	5,409,955
May	393,428	101,921	663,415	963,564	-	542,305	2,664,633
June	2,011,095	509,952	2,000,531	688,320	-	1,622,863	6,832,761
July	2,316,079	571,311	3,017,453	1,525,561	-	474,953	7,905,357
August	5,967,929	1,535,397	7,919,513	1,103,787	1,165,351	421,000	18,112,977
September	4,795,938	1,177,166	7,224,237	1,667,157	800,266	475,900	16,140,664
October	7,914,509	1,971,682	11,630,147	2,138,169	429,849	325,700	24,410,056
November	8,557,207	2,063,296	12,869,461	1,711,733	1,083,009	273,200	26,557,906
December	8,130,628	2,687,943	7,411,589	1,707,300	868,847	168,500	20,974,807
Total	44,945,328	11,806,145	57,894,123	13,752,390	4,347,322	10,614,089	143,359,397

Source data: (Microsoft excel) Non-oil revenue data/ Ministry of Finance and Planning

Figure 1 –above non-oil Revenue analysis graph from accounts/treasury

Figure2: Source data: Non-Oil Revenue report South Sudan Civil Aviation report
 Figure 2 -Revenue statistics analysis from accounts/treasury office (Source: Field Survey, april, 2021)

Table: Being Summary non-oil revenue report in SSP and USD as at Jan-Nov-2017 of Civil Aviation at Juba International Airport

Months	Amount SSP	Amount USD
January	5,504,583	447,781
February	3,496,264	293,954
March	5,349,434	308,912
April	5,409,955	347,384
May	2,664,633	422,278
June	6,832,761	932,560
July	7,905,357	468,237
August	18,112,977	405,831
September	16,140,664	621,164
October	24,410,056	421,816
November	26,557,906	492,085
December	20,974,807	201,200
Total	143,359,397	5,363,202

Source data: (Microsoft excel) Non-oil revenue/ Ministry of Finance and Planning

4.6. Non-oil Revenue report South Sudan Civil aviation report in SSP as From: Jan-Dec 2018

Months	Landing	Navigation	Security	Passengers	Parking	Others	Total SSP
January	7,805,502	1,763,381	8,054,439	2,533,474	307,306	74,500	20,538,602
February	4,156,650	1,020,958	5,801,238	1,176,896	500,478	136,000	12,792,220
March	5,015,189	1,236,072	6,148,216	1,876,976	610,824	-	14,887,277
April	4,924,134	1,105,172	6,667,209	677,722	1,928,316	-	15,302,553
May	4,035,884	773,514	4,920,206	1,226,126	1,475,580	1,000	12,432,310
June	6,601,473	1,671,849	8,132,138	284,984	2,406,013	-	19,096,457
July	3,368,794	823,362	5,283,313	-	1,056,926	-	10,532,395
August	5,852,715	1,300,282	5,897,871	-	1,570,627	-	14,621,495
September	3,064,194	536,518	3,210,288	-	972,303	-	7,783,303
October	3,919,108	929,461	5,534,598	-	1,453,636	-	11,836,803
November	6,349,869	2,092,092	6,494,031	-	959,216	-	15,895,208
December	4,833,356	892,902	5,906,061	-	678,215	-	12,310,534
Total	59,926,868	14,145,563	72,049,608	7,776,178	13,919,440	211,500	168,029,157

Source data: (Microsoft excel) Non-oil revenue/ Ministry of Finance and Planning

Being Summary non-oil revenue report as at Jan-Nov-2018 of Civil Aviation Juba International Airport

Months	Amount SSP	Amount USD
January	20,538,602	747,755
February	12,792,220	524,852
March	14,887,277	588,401
April	15,302,553	549,004
May	12,432,310	418,771
June	19,096,457	169,864
July	10,532,395	48,738
August	14,621,495	51,134
September	7,783,303	52,662
October	11,836,803	495,037
November	15,895,208	196,345
December	12,310,534	272,980
Total	168,029,157	4,115,543

Source data: Non-oil revenue Ministry of Finance and Planning

4.7. Non-oil Revenue report South Sudan Civil aviation report in USD as From: Jan-Dec 2019

Months	Landing	Navigation	Security	Passenger	Parking	Total USD
January	660,174	18,505	42,987	-	450	722,116
February	70,409	15,287	44,403	-	1,633	131,732
March	74,118	18,353	58,070	-	1,675	152,216
April	61,168	15,152	46,775	-	1,655	124,750
May	88,452	21,938	64,998	-	1,955	177,343
June	58,144	14,464	44,518	-	1,710	118,836
July	42,506	2,519	9,387	-	180	54,592
August	145,741	-	-	-	-	145,741
September	91,599	-	-	-	-	91,599
October	75,668	-	-	-	-	75,668
November	38,949	-	-	-	-	38,949
December	73,475	-	-	-	-	73,475
Total	1,480,403	106,218	311,138	-	9,258	1,907,017

Source data: (Microsoft excel) Non-oil revenue/ Ministry of Finance and Planning

Being Summary non-oil revenue as at Jan-Nov-2019 of Civil Aviation Juba International Airport

Months	Amount SSP	Amount USD
January	27,000,772.00	722,116.00
February	10,918,816.00	131,732.00
March	15,855,802.00	152,216.00

April	12,009,841.00	124,750.00
May	12,205,697.00	177,343.00
June	7,046,978.00	118,836.00
July	9,413,705.00	54,592.00
August	10,774,627.00	145,741.00
September	5,488,099.00	91,599.00
October	9,625,868.00	75,668.00
November	3,079,286.00	38,949.00
December	4,585,513.00	73,475.00
Total	128,005,004.00	1,907,017.00

Source data: (Microsoft excel) Non-oil revenue data/ Ministry of Finance and Planning

4.8. Non-oil Revenue report South Sudan Civil aviation report in USD as From: Jan-Dec 2020

Months	Landing	Navigation	Security	Passengers	Parking	Total SSP
January	5,220,581	-	-	-	-	5,220,581
February	5,359,639	-	-	-	-	5,359,639
March	5,936,659	-	-	-	-	5,936,659
April	5,296,512	-	-	-	-	5,296,512
May	3,712,021	-	-	-	-	3,712,021
June	4,520,427	-	-	-	-	4,520,427
July	3,591,324	-	-	-	-	3,591,324
August	3,202,518	-	-	-	-	3,202,518
September	5,768,140	-	-	-	-	5,768,140
October	6,478,233	-	-	-	-	6,478,233
November	5,305,321	-	-	-	-	5,305,321
December	5,234,483	-	-	-	-	5,234,483
Total	59,625,858	-	-	-	-	59,625,858

Source data: (Microsoft excel) Non-oil revenue data/ Ministry of Finance and Planning

The above table showed that there was no collection for full year in navigation, security, passengers' fees and parking fees due to pandemic COVID-19 infection this has led to decline of non-oil revenue collection in South Sudan aviation Authority

Table: Being Summary non-oil revenue collected report as at Jan-Nov-2020 of Civil Aviation Juba International Airport

Months	Amount \$	Amount SSP
January	110,259	5,220,581
February	58,137	5,359,639
March	98,623	5,936,659
April	2,915	5,296,512
May	26,592	3,712,021
June	27,768	4,520,427
July	26,250	3,591,324
August	33,354	3,202,518
September	40,456	5,768,140
October	62,289	6,478,233
November	59,607	5,305,321
December	70,301	5,234,483
Total	616,551	59,625,858

Source data: (Microsoft excel) Non-oil revenue data/ Ministry of Finance and Planning

Figure 3 -Revenue statistics analysis from accounts/treasury office

Figure 4 -Revenue statistics analysis from accounts/treasury office (Source: Field Survey, april, 2021)

4.9. Being Non-Oil Revenue Collected report in South Sudanese pound SSP from 2017 to 2020 JIA

Months	2017	2018	2019	2020	Total
January	5,504,583	20,538,602	27,000,772.00	5,220,581	58,264,538
February	3,496,264	12,792,220	10,918,816.00	5,359,639	32,566,939
March	5,349,434	14,887,277	15,855,802.00	5,936,659	42,029,172
April	5,409,955	15,302,553	12,009,841.00	5,296,512	38,018,861
May	2,664,633	12,432,310	12,205,697.00	3,712,021	31,014,661
June	6,832,761	19,096,457	7,046,978.00	4,520,427	37,496,623
July	7,905,357	10,532,395	9,413,705.00	3,591,324	31,442,781
August	18,112,977	14,621,495	10,774,627.00	3,202,518	46,711,617
September	16,140,664	7,783,303	5,488,099.00	5,768,140	35,180,206
October	24,410,056	11,836,803	9,625,868.00	6,478,233	52,350,960
November	26,557,906	15,895,208	3,079,286.00	5,305,321	50,837,721
December	20,974,807	12,310,534	4,585,513.00	5,234,483	43,105,337
Total	143,359,397	168,029,157	128,005,004.00	59,625,858	499,019,416

Source data: (Microsoft excel) Non-oil revenue data/ Ministry of Finance and Planning

Figure 5: Non-Oil Revenue analysis report in South Sudanese pound SSP from 2017 to 2020

Four years summary civil aviation JIA report in SSP

Months	2017	2018	2019	2020	Total
Summary collection	143,359,397	168,029,157	128,005,004.00	59,625,858	499,019,416

Source data: (Microsoft excel) Non-oil revenue/ Ministry of Finance and Planning

Four years line chart showing non revenue collection summary 2017-2020

Figure 6 -Revenue statistics analysis from accounts/treasury office

Figure 6: Non-Oil Revenue analysis report in South Sudanese pound SSP from 2016 to 2017

Non-oil Revenue by Tax

Sales	74,7 72,8 08	89,6 89,3 45	110, 738, 554	95,1 70,8 87	107, 276, 571	106, 286, 750	99,1 08,3 71	126, 768, 237	158, 263, 084	144,4 93,39 4	104, 584, 612	120, 895, 672	1,33 8,04 8,28 5
Advance Income Tax	17,2 08,0 74	18,3 69,7 73	24,7 82,5 38	20,4 47,4 18	23,5 71,6 04	21,8 12,1 76	20,2 00,4 97	23,1 39,3 62	33,1 63,7 22	29,96 3,562	24,2 77,2 92	23,8 09,8 45	280, 745, 863
Total Tax Collected by Customs on behalf of Taxation	117,6 65,82 3	133,33 8,016	169,97 9,681	142,14 2,946	158,77 3,299	166,35 7,424	155,30 3,534	188,17 6,176	257,3 07,86 0	225,877 ,280	166,87 0,585	202,2 85,61 6	2,084,0 78,239
Total Domes tic Tax Revenu e	468, 742, 277	348, 488, 498	457, 289, 115	461, 291, 150	392, 983, 840	495, 019, 788	486, 577, 690	620, 956, 394	664, 418, 789	1,654 ,471, 713	743, 080, 193	730, 841, 857	7,52 4,16 1,30 3
Custom s Duties /Fees	43,0 89,0 05	74,4 15,5 24	79,8 13,7 29	60,0 52,4 02	72,3 30,4 03	130, 919, 159	71,5 55,7 27	86,4 39,5 09	106, 968, 829	97,85 3,499	77,6 20,8 86	52,2 93,6 76	953, 352, 348

Non oil Revenue collected 2016-2017 in SSP

	Jul-16	Aug-16	Sep-16	Oct-16	Nov-16	Dec-16	Jan-17	Feb-17	Mar-17	Apr-17
Series1	980,616	490,683	1,332,511	1,241,211	2,102,351	1,407,891	913,963	1,556,391	1,614,191	5,966,920

Other non- Tax revenu e	22,6 49,0 70	44,0 33,1 35	46,8 69,5 90	47,16 7,277	134, 677, 407	65,1 00,7 26	102, 901, 123	77,7 20,4 79	130, 782, 311	109,5 88,06 2	136, 909, 717	122, 799, 204	1,041 ,198, 101
Total revenu e collecti on for the month	534, 480, 352	466, 937, 157	583, 972, 434	568, 510, 829	599, 991, 650	691, 039, 673	661, 034, 539	785, 116, 382	902, 169, 929	1,861 ,913, 274	957, 610, 796	905, 934, 737	9,51 8,71 1,75 2

Source data: (Microsoft excel) Non-oil revenue data/ Ministry of Finance and Planning

TAX REVENUE BY TAX TYPE: July 2015 - May 2016

Tax Type	Jul-15	Aug-15	Sep-15	Oct-15	Nov-15	Dec-15	Jan-16	Feb-16	Mar-16	Apr-16	May-16	Jun-16
Directorate of Taxation												
Personal Income (Private)	9,583,511	12,887,866	20,885,176	12,947,249	14,037,867	40,009,456	28,948,858	58,319,405	278,645,782	95,681,940	77,877,992	133,380,535
Personal Income (Public)	14,821,494	13,967,632	17,614,557	12,261,132	17,195,267	11,663,022	23,172,398	64,370	54,812,633	59,035	80,490,357	109,015,484
Business Profits Tax	12,512,927	1,380,255	447,973	22,921,265	1,351,686	944,042	27,048,185	4,790,395	41,540,159	75,441,834	1,398,239	142,705,518
Excise Tax	11,038,693	10,288,258	7,084,799	6,899,542	12,746,234	8,761,273	11,410,600	18,352,371	14,018,148	23,875,888	18,466,638	22,263,986
Sales	6,152,710	1,439,600	1,582,277	2,558,180	3,901,385	4,040,215	1,441,267	5,176,444	12,431,130	8,115,084	2,464,821	4,978,593
Advance Income Tax										0	0	0
Miscellaneous/BoSS	227,043	214,152	214,874	227,956	219,958	5,986,381	958,160	964,498	1,056,987	4,607,063	816,323	0
Total Domestic Tax Collection	54,336,378	40,177,763	47,829,656	57,815,324	49,452,397	71,404,389	92,979,468	87,667,483	402,504,839	207,780,844	181,514,370	412,344,116
Excise	6,181,559	7,063,518	6,000,084	4,251,154	4,904,782	10,241,258	26,188,588	24,679,336	26,001,688	32,079,430	33,144,673	31,882,300
Sales	25,584,025	24,230,210	20,148,656	17,672,885	21,348,463	37,819,795	89,026,653	99,683,989	113,790,084	134,096,715	123,307,544	136,347,102
Advance Income Tax	6,049,722	5,756,537	4,860,870	4,317,798	5,267,384	8,742,880	31,911,861	24,317,093	27,372,742	40,146,089	28,607,637	28,935,591
Total Tax Collected by Customs for Taxation	37,815,306	37,050,265	31,009,610	26,241,837	31,520,629	56,803,933	147,127,102	148,680,418	167,164,514	206,322,234	185,059,854	197,164,993
Total Tax Revenue	92,151,684	77,228,028	78,839,266	84,057,161	80,973,026	128,208,322	240,106,570	236,347,901	569,669,353	414,103,078	366,574,224	609,509,109
Customs Duties/Fees	14,527,438	12,755,169	12,080,399	10,777,357	12,532,922	21,111,020	53,369,747	62,262,471	59,692,445	75,513,584	75,187,036	83,337,432
Other non-Tax revenue	12,748,640	10,690,617	12,396,290	9,098,271	4,266,000	17,037,741	15,417,510	47,328,830	18,527,951	40,161,204	37,103,854	46,818,197
Total revenue for month	119,427,762	100,673,814	103,315,955	103,932,789	97,771,948	166,357,083	308,893,827	345,939,201	647,889,750	529,777,866	478,865,114	739,664,738
			323,417,531			368,061,820			1,302,722,778			1,748,307,717
Total annual collection 2015/2016 (July-June)												3,742,509,847

Source data: (Microsoft excel) Non-oil revenue data/ Ministry of Finance and Planning

Sources of non-oil revenue both Central Government and State Government

	Central Government	State Government
1	Landing Fees	Shops and kiosks rates
2	Fees/Fines/License	License Fee
3	Rent	Slaughter slab fee
4	Grants from foreign government	Cattle Tax
5	Taxes on Sales of Goods and services	Canoe fees, Bicycles, Trucks, Wheel barrow, Carts and Canoe,
6	Land tax	Domestic Animal License Fees
7	Social Contribution	Vehicle Parking fees
8	Taxes on property	Public Convenience, sewage and refuse disposal fees
9	Value added Tax	Burial Ground and religious places permit fees
10	Birth, and Death	Sign board and billboard advertisement permit fees
11	Registration fees	Radio and TV. License fees
12	Education tax	Stamp Duties (on Individuals Only)

13	With-holding tax (on companies)	Birth, and Death registration fees
14	Personal Income Tax (on employees)	Betting and Gaming Taxes
15	Customs Duties(i.e Import Duties and Export Duties)	Signboard and billboard advertisement permit fees
16	Excise Duties taxes	Market Fees (where Markets is financed by state Government)
17	Miscellaneous non-oil Revenues (e.g. farming , rents on property)	Radio and TV. License fees
18	Radio and TV. License fees	Business Premises and registration levies
19	Stamp duties (on corporate bodies)	property income
		Stamp Duties (on Individuals Only)
		Birth, and Death registration fees

Recommendations of the Study

The efficiency of the South Sudan tax system should be improved on by combining royalties and profit sensitive taxes with close attention to details and implementation. The perceived links between paying tax and enjoying the benefits of public spending should be strengthened. Increasing awareness of this relationship can clearly be constructive for the economy of South Sudan as a whole. Non-oil revenue transparent tax laws should be enacted to regulate the tax regimes in South Sudan with a view to eliminating the problems of implementation of good tax reforms policies. The tax base in South Sudan should be as broad as possible since this can minimize tax distortions and non-oil revenue collection losses. Frequent changes made in the tax structure by relevant tax authorities by way of tax policy should either be avoided or minimized, since it increases enforcement, compliance and efficiency costs, thus affecting production and business decisions. Non-oil revenue collection body should be strengthened with training on modern computerizes tax collection system in relation to East African Community standard. Other sources of non- oil revenue that are not in practice such as cattle tax, canoes and Wheel barrows, fishing licensing, Burial Ground and religious places permit fees, Betting and Gaming Taxes, Public Convenience, sewage and refuse disposal fees should intensified, Slaughter slab fee, Signboard and billboard advertisement permit fees, Although such collection are done by local and state Government there is need for those taxes to be unified or centralized under the management of National Government. Trucks Parking fees at the borders such Nimule corridor Uganda border, Nadapal kenya Renk Sudan border, Kaya Uganda and DRC Congo, border and within the capital city and state cities should be properly channel to national treasury or National Revenue Authority (NRA) South Sudan

Diversify the economy

For an economy to be stable and sustainable in South Sudan there has to be a diversification of its sources of non-oil revenue. Indeed, there are compelling reasons for other export-oriented sectors of the South Sudan economy, especially in the agricultural, mining and agro-allied areas to be embraced and addressed to enhance their contributions to the country's Gross Domestic Product (GDP). Economic diversification has a biblical origin. The Bible records four rivers that flow into the Garden of Eden. Each of these rivers signifies a resource, one of which is gold. Even for an individual, resource flow should ideally not be restricted to only one source. For South Sudan, this is the time to pursue the diversification of the economy with a frequent vigor. This suggests that some erstwhile moribund but now promising revenue sources like Agriculture, trade, tourism, manufacturing, etc must be re-activated and made functional at the three tiers of government. South Sudan is richly endowed with natural resources including some million hectares of arable land, fresh water sources covering million hectares, kilometers of coastline and a range of ecological belts and arable farming lands. This natural and favorable geological setting enables the country to produce a wide variety of agricultural and industrial materials which exist in their primary form all over the country. The conversion of these raw materials into industrially usable form,

through Research and Development (R&D) remains the greatest challenge to South Sudan. In diversifying the economy therefore, government should identify and priorities some critical raw materials and adequately fund their development. Government should achieve this through a Public-Private Partnership (PPP) arrangement, while the Raw Materials Research and Development Council, which should coordinate this, should be adequately funded.

Others non-oil Revenue Sectors

A sustainable development of the iron and steel sector is critical to the overall development and industrialization of South Sudan. Indeed, there is an urgent need for industrial revolution in South Sudan. To achieve this, South Sudan is to embark on such policy options as resuscitating its institutions/agencies like technical colleges all over the country, the Steel Rolling Mill Aluminum Smelter Company, National iron ore Mining project, the non-functional Steel Company(SC) Steel Complex, etc. Government involvement in the sector is necessary because of its capital-intensive nature. A Public-Private Partnership PPP arrangement can also be adopted to improve the sectors.

Review the Legislative List for effective national resource Mobilization

In order to guarantee effective sub-national non-oil revenue collection, there is the need for amendment to certain legislations that presently inhibit the states and local governments in terms of non-oil revenue collection. For instance, there is the need for creating legislative enabling environment that will support growth and development of private business especially at the grassroots level. Many local governments and states in South Sudan are endowed with abundant natural resources but the bulk of these resources are illegally exploited by unknown persons. It is important to note that despite the abundant mineral resources in many states of the federation, their exploitations being carried out illegally and in haphazard manner largely because the mining of mineral resources is an item on the exclusive legislative list which only the central government can engage in.

Expand South Sudan's Tax Base

South Sudan's tax base remains very narrow, despite promising growth in key states of South Sudan. In most developed countries, tax revenues are dominant contributor to national treasury. For South Sudan however, the Ministry of Finance estimates in May 2013 that the country's Tax-GDP rate stood at roughly 7%, compared to nearly 15% for neighboring economies like East African countries. This suggests that a lot of non-oil revenue could still be derived from taxation in South Sudan. According to The South Sudan Economic cluster Group, (2020-2021), Federal Inland Revenue service(FIRS) lowered Personal Income Tax (PIT) from 5% to 18% in 2013, while leaving the Corporate Income Tax(CIT) unchanged at 30%. There is still much to achieve in tax collection in South Sudan. Tourism, for instance, is one area where South Sudan can increase revenue generation. South Sudan is endowed with a fair share of tourism potentials including cultural festivals and celebrations, historical monuments and museums, natural endowment/man-made attractions, and so on. The South Sudan Tourism development Corporation (NTDC), National Council for Arts and Culture (NCAC), national Commission for Museums and Monuments (NCMM), and National Tourism should be re-positioned to develop and implement policies on tourism towards enhancing tax revenues from the sector. The informal sector has the potentials to greatly improve South Sudan's tax revenues if properly organized. Presently, a large number of informal sector actors are not captured in national accounting, simply because of cumbersome registration processes. The sector should be re-organized through a simple registration process towards formalizing its activities.

Tackle Tax Evasion

Tax evasion has been a constant challenge in South Sudan's revenue drive as most individuals and corporate organizations have the culture of tax evasion. It is estimated that In March 2013 South Sudan had lost some N90billion (\$567 million) to the grey market in automobiles

alone since 2009. To effectively achieve reduction of tax evasion, there is a need to run tax education campaigns to sensitize various stakeholders, including traditional leaders, clergymen and community leaders to encourage tax compliance within the informal sector. Another related suggestion is the outsourcing of tax collection. State government has as part of its success factors the outsourcing of tax collection to private bodies. As a result, the state grew its tax revenue from SSP billion) in 2007 to billion in early 2013 with internally generated revenue (IGR) contributing 75% of all receipts (The South Sudan Economic cluster Group,). Government should institutionalize a number of tax incentives it has started, including the granting of pioneer status to export producing enterprises, provision of tax holiday from income tax up to five years, granting a tax credit of 20% of cost for a period of five years to engineering companies which use a minimum of 60% locally sourced raw materials for production, and so on.

Improve Infrastructure

Massive infrastructural renewal becomes imperative if South Sudan is to achieve its goal of economic diversification and improvement in non-oil revenue sources in South Sudan. Many small scale enterprises have been forced out of business due to exorbitant cost of production as a result of added cost of electricity/power generation. South Sudan governments, especially at the federal level need to provide conducive working business environment for effective non-oil revenue collection and mobilization. Indeed, government may have to provide basic infrastructural facilities like good roads, electricity, watered to ensure sustainable development of non-oil sector. Government may consider a reform of the sector just as it did to the telecom, communication and power systems. This involves ending government monopoly by allowing private firms to bid for the rights to build and or operate under the oversight of a new regulatory commission. These same gestures can be extended to pipelines, gas and refineries. When this is done, manufacturing will become simultaneously competitive and manufacturing exports would grow.

Conclusion

The mobilization of non-oil revenue is an important policy objective. South Sudan Governments in the short run can do better or to alter structural determinants of the tax revenue (such as composition of value added), however, they have the powers to change other factors which are internal to her that influence tax revenue, such as economic policies, the level of corruption, and the quality of tax administration. The wide divergence between the effective and statutory tax rates in South Sudan indicates that there is scope for raising tax revenue without increasing tax rates by enforcing tax and customs administrations, reducing tax exemptions (especially in the areas of manufacturing), and fighting fraud and corruption. Nevertheless, one must be realistic in terms of improvement in revenue ratios that can be reasonably expected to be achieved in South Sudan, given the low level of development and the heavily agricultural and informal character of the economy. Indeed, optimizing tax mobilization and carrying out reforms can be achieved only when there is a strong political will and leadership to adopt the necessary measures. Overall, it is shown from the study that non-oil revenues lead to effect on economic growth. The study findings revealed that, Non-oil revenues taxes have more significant positive effects on the South Sudan economy than direct taxation. Only one tax component in the study (i.e., CIT) had a positive coefficient in the study. This implies that indirect taxes, which seem to exert a more general impact on individuals, in a country actually stimulate the ratio economic activities in the country. Direct taxes have significant negative effects on the South Sudan economic growth, especially in the long run. Thus, taxes which have more personal implications tend to yield debilitating effects on economic growth impact. This suggests that efficiency of direct tax management is much lesser than that of indirect tax management in South Sudan. The level of tax administration

tends to generate instability in the economic system in South Sudan. The results showed that a proper mix of direct and indirect taxes in South Sudan will result in highly productive tax regimes that would ensure long run non-oil revenue and economic improvements. Road toll to be introduced for improvement collection should be introduced for the maintenance of road to improve transportation. Cattle taxes should be introduced since cattle are the source of non-oil revenue.

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